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List of Acronyms

CR	Cosmic Ray
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
IGY	International Geophysical Year
NM	Neutron Monitor
PAD	Pitch-Angle Distribution
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SQ	Science Question
YF	Yield Function

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Neutron Monitors (NMs) are essential ground-based instruments for studying primary Cosmic Rays (CRs), particularly Solar Energetic Particles (SEPs). Sensitive in the wide energy range of 1–1000 GeV, NMs detect secondary particles produced when CRs interact with the atmosphere. Accurate interpretation requires a well-defined Yield Function (YF) that describes the response of NM as a function of particle rigidity, arrival direction, and atmospheric depth, essentially linking NM count rates to primary CR flux. Using global NM networks, researchers can analyze Ground Level Enhancements (GLEs) by exploiting geomagnetic differences between stations—effectively using Earth’s magnetic field as a natural spectrometer. Monte Carlo simulations, conducted with PLANETOCOSMICS and GEometry ANd Tracking (GEANT)4, model atmospheric cascades and NM response at various altitudes. Recent advances include the development of mini NMs, which are more compact but less sensitive than standard 6NM64 detectors due to their smaller surface area and reduced moderator volume. This results in lower count rates and sensitivity to CR variations. However, high-altitude deployment enhances their SEP detection capability. In this work, registration efficiency of the mini-NM has been simulated, showing good agreement with earlier results. Additionally, a new yield function for the standard 6NM64 has been computed for oblique proton incidence in the 0.7–20 GV rigidity range, aimed specifically at GLE analysis.

1 Introduction

SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (**SPEARHEAD**) will provide answers to three Science Questions (**SQs**):

1. How are protons accelerated beyond 100 MeV and electrons beyond 1 MeV in solar eruptions?
2. What are the release times and spectral characteristics of near-relativistic particles from solar eruptions?
3. How do coronal and interplanetary structures affect the transport processes of very high energetic particles?

Ground Level Enhancements (**GLEs**) observed by Neutron Monitors (**NMs**) play a crucial role in understanding the acceleration and transport of high-energy particles from solar eruptions. **GLEs** are rare events where solar energetic particles (**SEPs**), primarily protons, are accelerated to such high energies—typically above 500 MeV—that they can penetrate Earth’s magnetosphere and atmosphere, producing secondary particles detected by ground-based **NMs** (Shea & Smart 2012; Papaioannou 2023). Apparently these observations provide direct evidence that solar eruptions are capable of accelerating protons well beyond 100 MeV. By analyzing the intensity, timing, and global distribution of **GLEs**, scientists can infer details about the underlying acceleration mechanisms, distinguishing between rapid flare-associated acceleration and sustained shock-driven acceleration by coronal mass ejections (**CMEs**) (see details in Kouloumvakos et al. 2024). The reconstructed energy spectra and anisotropy patterns from multi-station neutron monitor data provide critical constraints on how and where this extreme acceleration occurs (see e.g. Mishev et al. 2014; Kocharov et al. 2017; Mishev et al. 2021; Kocharov et al. 2023). In addition to acceleration, **GLEs** studies using **NMs** observations also shed light on particle release times and transport through the interplanetary medium (Masson et al. 2009; Musset et al. 2023). The precise timing of particle arrival at different stations allows researchers to estimate when the particles were released at the Sun and how their paths were influenced by solar and heliospheric structures (Masson et al. 2012; Moraal & McCracken 2012). Consequently, **GLEs** represent prime candidates for providing answers to all three **SQs** of **SPEARHEAD**. Nonetheless, the study of primary **CR** particle characteristics, specifically **SEPs**, from ground-based data records is a major challenge. As noted here above, a convenient instrument for such purpose is the **NM**. In general, the **NM** is an instrument that measures the intensity of high-energy **CR** particles. It allows to accumulate continuous recordings of the secondary **CR** hadron component. As a result, **NM** measurements provide a basis for studying variations in the intensity of the interplanetary **CR** spectrum. Due to the decreasing energy spectrum of the primary **CRs**, neutron monitors (**NMs**) are particularly sensitive to the low-energy part of the **CR** spectrum, typically between 1 and 20 GeV.

The introduction of the **NM** as a continuous recorder of the primary **CR** intensity was enabled by the pioneering design of Simpson (Simpson et al. 1953). On that basis a 12-tube **NM** was constructed during the International Geophysical Year (**IGY**) 1957-1958 (Simpson 1957). The **IGY NM** was used world-wide as a detector to study cosmic ray variations. Based on long-term measurement series, the design of **NMs** was optimized by significantly increasing the amount of lead producer per unit area. This enhancement led to higher counting rates and resulted in the development of the **NM64** (Hatton & Carmichael 1964; Hatton 1971). An illustration with the main components of **NM64** is given in Fig. 1. The measurements performed by the worldwide network of **NMs** are used for the estimation of spectral and angular characteristics of **SEP**s near Earth. It is important to establish a relationship between **NM** count rate and primary particle flux (Bütikofer 2018). The **NM** Yield Function (**YF**) accounts for the full complexity of atmospheric cascade development and the propagation of secondary particles through the Earth’s atmosphere, as well as the **NM**’s detection efficiency for secondary cosmic ray particles.

The purpose of this document, within the **SPEARHEAD** project, is to provide updated and internally consistent **YFs** for both standard **6NM64** detectors and mini-**NM**. The emphasis is placed entirely on

Figure 1: Sketch of a standard 6NM64 NM. The NM consists of a moderator, which reduces the energy of neutrons i.e. increasing the probability of an absorption inside the counter while also providing a reflecting medium for low energy neutrons. The moderator material is usually low density polyethylene. The Lead Producer surrounds the moderator, and provides a thick large-nucleus target for incident particles. A large nucleus such as lead is preferred as the neutron production rate per unit mass of a material is roughly proportional to the mass. Surrounding the lead is an outer moderator, usually referred to as the Reflector, which serves to contain low energy neutrons produced in interactions within the lead and to reject unwanted low energy neutrons (external evaporation neutrons) produced in the local surroundings from entering into the detector. Adapted from (Bütikofer 2018) under CC BY 4.0.

new computational results. The present document introduces a new generation of YFs for the NM64 detector, explicitly extended to oblique primary-particle incidence up to 60° , together with separate YFs for three characteristic atmospheric depths. It also includes new GEANT4-based simulations of the mini-NM registration efficiency and the corresponding YF at 700 g cm^{-2} , using a modeling framework designed to ensure reproducibility and methodological clarity.

2 NM yield functions

In order to employ a ground-based detector, particularly a NM as a primary particle detector against the incoming CR particles of galactic and/or solar origin, it is necessary to establish a proper relationship between the count rate and primary CR flux (Clem & Dorman 2000).

Primary CRs that are not reflected by the Earth's geomagnetic field penetrate the atmosphere, and interact with atmospheric constituents, i.e. undergo nuclear interactions driving the secondary generation of high-energy particles (Dorman 2004; Mishev 2023). These interactions produce secondary particles—primarily mesons (pions, kaons) and nucleons—which further interact or decay, generating extensive atmospheric showers. The resulting cascade of secondary particles, including neutrons, muons, and other components, propagates through the atmosphere, with a fraction reaching ground level, where they are detected by NMs (see details in Dorman 2004).

The counting rate of a NM is presented as:

$$N(P_c, h, t) = \int_{P_c}^{\infty} \sum_i Y_i(P, h) J_i(P, t) dP = \int_{P_c}^{\infty} W_T(P, h, t) dP \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Previously used nine segments angular scheme distribution above a **NM**, indicating viewing directions (zenith angles 0, 16 and 32 degrees. Adapted from [Cramp et al. \(1997\)](#).

where $N(P_c, h, t)$ is the NM counting rate, P_c is the local geomagnetic cutoff rigidity as a function of viewing direction, h is the atmospheric depth and t represents time. The term $Y_i(P, h)$ represents the **NM** yield function (**YF**) for primaries of particle type i , $J_i(P, t)$ represents the rigidity spectrum of primary particle of type i at time t and W_T is the total differential response function.

Accordingly, the **NM** yield function (**YF**) is defined as:

$$Y_i(P, h) = \sum_i \int \int A_i(E, \theta) F_{i,j}(P, h, E, \theta) dE d\Omega \quad (2)$$

where $A_i(E, \theta)$ is the detector area multiplied by registration efficiency, $F_{i,j}$ is the differential flux of secondary particles (neutrons, protons, muons, pions) per primary i , E is respectively the secondary particle's energy, θ is the angle of incidence of secondaries and Ω is the solid angle ([Flükiger et al. 2008](#)). Therefore, a **YF** incorporates both the propagation of particles through the Earth's atmosphere and the detection response of a **NM** against secondary particles such as neutrons, protons, muons and pions.

The method for analyzing **GLEs** using **NM** data is based on the fact that **NM** stations located at different geographic regions sample different ranges of particle rigidity and asymptotic arrival directions due to geomagnetic shielding and atmospheric effects. In that sense, the geomagnetosphere acts as a large-scale natural spectrometer, independent of whether the detected particles originate from **SEPs** or Galactic Cosmic Rays (**GCRs**) ([Bieber & Evenson 1995](#); [Bütikofer 2018](#); [Mishev et al. 2021](#)). Therefore, using the measurements of as many as possible **NMs** (for details see, [Mishev & Usoskin 2020](#), and the discussion therein), depending on the complexity of the event, and by modeling of the global **NM** network response with n model parameters, while constraining the model using the measurements from

m experimental data points (that is the number of **NMs**). Under explicit assumptions regarding the primary particle energy spectrum, composition and Pitch-Angle Distribution (**PAD**), the model parameters are optimized by minimizing the discrepancies between modeled and measured **NM** count rates, allowing the determination of the most probable spectral characteristics, **PAD**, and apparent source direction of **GLEs** (Cramp et al. 1997; Bombardieri et al. 2006; Vashenyuk et al. 2006; Mishev et al. 2014). The response of each **NM** during the modeling is computed by convolution of the assumed primary **CR** spectrum $J(P,t)$ with the **NM** **YF** $Y(P,h)$ (for details see Clem & Dorman 2000).

Figure 3: Segments (from the center) of the sky over which the **NM** response was integrated during the modeling. Segment 1 (center) corresponds to vertical incidence, segments 2 (first from the central ring, North)–5 (first ring West), to 0–90–180–270 degrees inclination. Segments 6–9 and 10–13 correspond to an inclination of 30 and 45 degrees, respectively. Adapted from Mishev (2023) under CC BY 4.0.

In the general case, considering the contribution of oblique incidence **SEPs** to the **NM** response, which is particularly important for modeling strong and/or with complicated angular distribution events (Clem 1997), the relative count rate increase of a given **NM** during a **GLE** is modeled by:

$$\frac{\Delta N(P_{\text{cut}})}{N(t)} = \frac{\sum_k \int_{P_{\text{cut}}}^{P_{\text{max}}} J_{\text{sep}}(P,t) S_k(P) G_k(\alpha(P,t)) A_k(P) dP}{\sum_i \int_{P_{\text{cut}}}^{\infty} J_{\text{GCR}_i}(P,t) S_i(P) dP} \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta N(P_{\text{cut}})$ is the count rate increase due to solar particles, $N(t)$ is the count rate due to **GCRs**, J_{sep} is the rigidity spectrum of **SEPs**, $J_{\text{GCR}_i}(P,t)$ is the rigidity spectrum of the i component (proton or α -particle, etc...) of **GCRs** at a given time t , i.e. effectively accounting for the modulation. $G(\alpha(P,t))$ is the **PAD** (note that for **GCRs** the angular distribution is assumed to be isotropic). $A(P)$ is a discrete function with $A(P)=1$ for allowed trajectories and $A(P)=0$ for forbidden trajectories (Cooke et al. 1991). Function A is derived during the asymptotic direction computations. P_{cut} is the minimum rigidity cut-off of the station,

accordingly, P_{cut} is the maximum rigidity of SEPs considered in the model, whilst for GCR $P_{\text{max}} \rightarrow \infty$. S_k is the NMYF for vertical and for oblique incidence SEPs from various segments as proposed by Cramp et al. (1997), displayed in Fig. 2, and lately developed further by (Mishev 2023), plotted in Fig. 3. The central segment corresponds to vertical incidence, segments 2–5 for SEPs inclined of 15 degrees and azimuth angles 0–90–180–270 degrees, segments 6–9 and 10–13 correspond to an inclination of 30 and 45 degrees, respectively with the same azimuth angles as for 15 degrees inclination. We would like to stress that the asymptotic directions of the incoming SEPs are computed for each segment separately, that is, we have for in total 13 sets of asymptotic directions.

Figure 4: Newly computed yield function Y (YF) for CRs of a standard 6NM64 neutron monitor. Panel A: Y for primary protons at $1000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (sea level), Panel B: $700 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (about 3000 m a.s.l.) and Panel C: $500 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (about 5000 a.s.l.), as denoted in the legend. The figure is adapted from Mishev et al. (2019), with added YFs for incidence of 60° and 75° . See text for details.

In earlier GLE analyses, the assumption of vertical SEP incidence was commonly adopted, largely because it simplifies the unfolding procedure (Bütikofer & Flückiger 2013). While such an approximation may be adequate during phases when the particle distribution is nearly isotropic, it becomes unreliable when strong anisotropy dominates the early rise of a GLE (Cramp et al. 1997; Mishev et al. 2021). The importance of accounting for oblique incidence was first recognized in the work of Cramp et al. (1997), who introduced a nine-segment angular scheme (see Fig. 2) to represent different SEP arrival directions, although their analysis relied on pre-Monte Carlo NM response functions. Subsequent investigations by Clem (1997) and Mishev et al. (2019) refined this concept, with the latter incorporating YF computed at the actual altitude of each station. Building upon these developments, the present deliverable adopts an updated angular segmentation scheme in which the upper hemisphere is divided into discrete viewing

sectors: a central segment corresponding to vertical incidence and additional rings at 15° , 30° , and 45° zenith angles, each subdivided into the four classical azimuths (see Fig.3). This framework is further extended through new simulations up to 75° zenith angle, allowing us to quantify the contribution of more distant angular sectors to the total NM response and enabling a more robust reconstruction of highly anisotropic SEP fluxes, yet the contribution of SEPs with incidence greater than 45° is less than 3%. However, segments with inclination of $60\text{--}75^\circ$ could be important for studies of peculiar anisotropies (Gil et al. 2018). To obtain the updated NM YF at various atmospheric depths, we performed high-statistics

Figure 5: GEANT4 simulated registration efficiency for standard (Clem & Dorman 2000) and mini NM. Comparison with accelerator data is taken from Shibata et al. (1997) (see their Fig. 3), and Shibata et al. (1999) (see their Fig. 4).

Monte Carlo simulations of cosmic-ray-induced atmospheric cascades using the PLANETOCOSMICS tool (Desorgher et al. 2005), which is based on the GEANT4 particle transport framework (Agostinelli et al. 2003) and employs the NRLMSISE-00 atmospheric model (Picone et al. 2002). PLANETOCOSMICS simulates, in detail, the interactions and decays of nuclei, hadrons, muons, electrons and photons in the atmosphere across a broad energy range, yielding the differential fluxes of secondary particles at specified observation levels. Using these simulations, we calculated the secondary particle fluxes at each atmospheric depth and subsequently convolved them with the NM registration efficiency (Eq. 2). The updated registration efficiency follows the formalism of Clem & Dorman (2000) and incorporates contributions from secondary neutrons, protons, positive and negative pions, and muons (Clem & Dorman 2000; Mishev et al. 2013). The computations were performed separately for primary protons with energies between approximately 0.7 and 20 GeV/nucleon, and all results were normalized to one primary particle.

Several substantial improvements over earlier YF calculations were implemented, including greatly increased Monte Carlo statistics, a harmonized treatment of all relevant secondary species, explicit modeling of oblique primary incidence, and independent calculations for three characteristic atmospheric depths representing sea level, roughly 3000 m altitude, and roughly 5000 m altitude. These steps ensure that the resulting YFs are suitable for both mid-latitude and high-altitude polar monitoring stations and fully compatible with the requirements of contemporary GLE modeling. The updated YFs, illustrated in Fig. 4,

represent a significant advancement over the earlier work of [Mishev et al. \(2019\)](#), particularly through the reduction of statistical uncertainties in the simulated cascades and through the extension of the modeling to SEP incidence angles exceeding 45° . A dedicated analysis of the segment-wise contribution to the total NM response shows that particles arriving at zenith angles greater than 45° can typically be neglected; however, for exceptionally strong events (e.g., GLEs 5 and 8) or for events with complex temporal profiles, such as those recorded during October–November 1989 ([Cramp et al. 1993, 1995](#); [Mishev et al. 2021](#)), contributions from incidence angles approaching 60° become significant and must be included in the modeling. The resulting curves in Fig. 4 display the expected convergence at high rigidities and a clear dependence on atmospheric depth, with decreased sensitivity at high altitudes due to reduced overburden. The oblique-incidence simulations reveal that angular effects diminish significantly above a few GV, in agreement with expectations from cascade theory.

Figure 6: GEANT4 simulated yield function Y (YF) for CRs of a standard mini NM at $700 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (about 3000 m a.s.l.), compared with ([Flückiger et al. 2008](#)) parameterization, Monte Carlo computed YF ([Mangeard et al. 2016](#)) and recent computation ([Mishev et al. 2020](#)).

In order to calibrate worldwide NMs, the North-West University in Potchefstroom, South Africa, proposed the development of a calibration device [Moraal et al. \(2000\)](#). Accordingly, two small NMs were built in 2002. Lately, thanks to advances in electronics, the front-end electronics (i.e heads) have been redesigned. In addition, more efficient counter tubes became available, leading to the development of a mini NM, based on counters smaller than NM64, but more efficient ([Strauss et al. 2020](#)). It was recently shown that such instruments can attain count rates that approach those of standard NMs if they are placed at mountain locations of > 3000 m altitude. Most importantly, high-altitude polar stations are much more sensitive to SEPs ([Mishev & Poluianov 2021](#)). Therefore, the realistic information of the YF of

a mini NM is specifically important to precise modeling and analysis of GLEs. In this work, we simulated the registration efficiency of a single-tube mini NM, such as the one located in the DOME C polar station (Poluianov et al. 2015). The simulations were performed using the GEANT4 toolkit (Agostinelli et al. 2003). For the simulation of the registration efficiency, we employed the approach of Clem & Dorman (2000) in order to make further comparison.

The registration efficiency of the mini-NM (Fig.5) is lower compared to that of a standard 6NM64 configuration, primarily due to its smaller detector surface area, accordingly reduced compared to standard 6NM64 produced. Since the detection probability of secondary CR particles—particularly neutrons—is directly related to the geometric area and moderator volume of the monitor, a smaller active area results in a lower count rate and reduced sensitivity to variations in the primary cosmic ray flux. The computation of mini NM YFs at various altitudes, and designs as well as validation, is in progress, but the value of $700 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (about 3000 m a.s.l.) is already computed (see Fig. 6). We emphasize that this YF is specifically computed for the standard, i.e the lead NM at DOMC, while for other configurations, such as bare NMs and those with a larger number of detectors, the work is in progress.

3 Conclusions

In this work we computed a new generation of standard 6NM64 YFs, particularly for protons with oblique incidence. The YF is calculated in the 0.7–20 GV rigidity range, specifically aimed at GLE analysis. The newly computed mini NM YFs for $700 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (about 3000 m a.s.l.), which corresponds to the altitude of DOMC NM, the most sensitive stations in operation, (Poluianov et al. 2015; Mishev & Poluianov 2021) is presented in Fig. 6, while for the other altitudes the computation is in progress. We note that the new generation YFs, both for standard NM64 type detectors and mini-NMs, are computed within the range allowing for the analysis of GLEs in the existing gap, specifically for high-altitude polar stations Mishev & Poluianov (2021).

This current report constitutes the Deliverable 2.2 (D2.2) of SPEARHEAD which addresses updated NM YF, including:

- 1. A newly computed standard 6NM64 YF, extended to oblique incidence up to 75°**
- 2. A refined assessment of segment-wise contribution to the NM response using an updated angular segmentation scheme**
- 3. A new GEANT4-based mini-NM registration-efficiency simulation, harmonized with the Clem & Dorman (2000) formalism, enabling consistent treatment of hybrid monitoring networks**
- 4. A new mini-NM YF for $700 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ observation level, which corresponds to DOMC station.**

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